

FINANCIAL TECHNOLOGY AND BANKING SERVICES

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Abstract:

Economic frictions such as information asymmetries and economic forces such as economies of scale and scope give rise to financial intermediaries. These frictions and forces also shape market structure. While technological advances are not new to finance, digital innovation has brought major improvements in connectivity of systems, in computing power and cost, and in newly created and usable data. These improvements have alleviated transaction costs and given rise to new business models and new entrants. As technology has increased information exchange and reduced transaction costs, the production of financial services could be disaggregated. Specialized players have unbundled financial services, allowing consumers to find and assemble their preferred suites of products. However, classic economic forces remain relevant even in an age of digital production. Economies of scale and scope and network effects are present in many aspects of financial services production, including customer acquisition, funding, compliance activities, data and capital (including trust capital). Despite advances in technology, consumer search and assembly costs remain significant. These forces encourage re-bundling, and confer advantages to large multi-product providers, including technology (big tech) firms expanding into financial services from adjacent markets. The digital transformation of financial services gives rise to a set of important policy issues regarding competition, regulatory perimeters and ensuring a level playing field. Potential outcomes regarding competition, concentration and market composition include a “barbell” outcome composed of a few large providers and many niche players. Authorities must coordinate across financial regulation, competition, and industry regulatory bodies to manage trade-offs between stability and integrity, competition and efficiency, and consumer protection and privacy.

Introduction:

Crypto-assets are digital assets recorded on a distributed ledger. On 9 January 2019, ESMA and EBA each released a report on the current and future regulation of the EU crypto-assets market. ESMA notes that the majority of crypto-assets qualify as financial instruments under the Markets in Financial Instruments Directive (MiFID II); however national authorities face challenges in interpreting and adapting the existing requirements to the specific characteristics of crypto-assets. Meanwhile, a number of crypto-assets fall outside the current financial regulatory framework. The EBA report focuses on the applicability of the Electronic Money Directive and PSD II, and looks at issues arising in the context of crypto-asset wallet providers and crypto-asset trading platforms. The earliest and best known example of crypto-assets is crypto-currencies, a special type of virtual currencies. In this field, the EU has not yet adopted

any specific regulation. However, following up on a June 2017 Commission report, in December 2017, European legislators agreed to extend the scope of the Anti-money-laundering Directive to virtual currency exchanges and wallet providers. Fintech action plan and crowdfunding Having been invited by Parliament in a May 2017 own-initiative resolution to take more action in fintech sectors such as big data, cybersecurity, blockchain, interoperability, financial stability, financial and IT skills, the European Commission presented a fintech action plan in March 2018. The plan sets out 19 steps to promote innovative business models, the uptake of new technologies(e.g. artificial intelligence and cloud services), to increase cybersecurity and the integrity of the financial system, and to enhance further investor, consumer and data protection. It promotes innovation and regulatory certainty. It also envisages the introduction of regulatory sandboxes, which can be considered 'safe spaces' where (national) supervisors apply rules to fintech firms in a more flexible way so that businesses can test their models, products and services for a limited time and without being exposed to red tape. The EU FinTech Lab was set up to build capacity and knowledge among regulators and supervisors. It held its first meeting in June 2018. In this context, the Commission has put forward new rules to help EU crowdfunding platforms scale up. In March 2018, it tabled a proposal for a regulation aimed at introducing an optional EU regime to enable crowdfunding platforms to operate easily across the EU. Instead of facing differing regimes, platforms would have to comply with one set of rules only, both in their home market and in other Member States. The accompanying proposal for a directive amends the scope of MiFID II, adding crowdfunding service providers authorised under the proposed regulation to the list of exempted entities to which the scope of the directive does not apply.

Nowadays, people across the country has been entered to the era of revolution industry 4.0 where the process of daily human activities is carried out using the assistance of machine and technology. This is followed by the development of modern human’s lifestyle who are digitalized by technology. According to data by Hootsuite about Digital Around The World (2020) at least around 5.16 billion people worldwide are mobile phone users and around 4.57 billion people of them are internet users. The following data is the development of technology users in the world in 2020 :

Pictures 1. Digital Around The World (2020)

The diverse of needs in modern society require adequate and easy process of financial support so that in any transactional process it is more effective and efficient for consumers or users. This needs then led to the new business model using technology in financial sector namely financial technology or fintech.

Financial technology or fintech is the combination of financial service and technology that ultimately changes the conventional business model to moderate, which initially done by face-to-face transaction and brings a sum of cash, now people can make long-distance transactions that can be done directly from their smartphone. In the past, the financial processes were focused on the banking business which still used conventional service process where customers had to come directly to the bank, queued up, and made transactions which certainly took time and effort. Fintech provides technology-based financial services that can be easily accessed by users via smartphone so it can reduce time and energy. In addition, the use of technology can also reduce the risk of technical errors that might be occurred by officers or service provides in conventional financial services.

In my own country, Indonesia; fintech companies continue to grow from year to year. This is followed by research from (Harefa & Kennedy, 2018) investigated the numbers of fintech companies in Indonesia has significant growth where in 2019 there are already hundreds of fintech companies in Indonesia in multiple services. This phenomena also occurred in global area which according to data by Accenture.com (2019), global fintech investment continues to increase from last years. The following data is a graph of global fintech financing :

Pictures 2. Graph of Global Fintech Financing (2019)

The emergence of fintech is a form of disruptive innovation that can disrupt conventional financial business and change people’s behavior especially in meeting the financial needs. According to axiology perspective, there are 2 ways in facing the technology advances which are optimism and pessimism perspective. Optimism perspective sees the technology really helpful and can improve the welfare of its users. Based on previous research conducted by the author, this perspective can be supported by Technology Acceptant Model or (TAM) model

which said perceived of usefullness and perceived ease of use were variables that influence the use of technology including financial technology. Quick and easy transaction process is becoming an attraction to people to switch transactions electronically. In addition, time efficiency is a competitive advantage from fintech services where all of the transactions can be done using smartphone so it can reduce the possibility of wasting time as usually happens in conventional financial services (Pavlou, 2003). This feeling of easy and quick transaction process is a form of perceived of usefullness and perceived ease of use in the use of financial technology. This perspective lead to the intensity of use of fintech (Yang, Pang, Yen , & Tarn, 2015; Haidari & Tileng , 2018) .

But, beside the optimism perspective that shows positive views of the advanced of technology, there is pesimism perspective that views the technology as disruptive innovation who has negative impacts to the users. The research conducted by (Salanova, Llorens, & Cifre, 2013) explained that the use of internet communication technology or (ICT) can emerged the ICT fatigue or anxiety. This feelings of anxiety or fatigue is the form of perceived of risk (Pavlou, 2003; Yang, Pang, Yen , & Tarn, 2015) which refers to anxious or afraid about the risk of transaction failure or loss of funds from user's accounts. As we know, some fintech services such as e-payment, e-money, or e-wallet require users to deposit an amount of money in user's account on fintech apps before making certain transaction. This process can lead to perceived of risk because those money can not be seen directly by the user, unlike the conventional financial services that has transparancy on its process.

In some countries, including Indonesia, there were problems happened such as online transaction errors in user's account, the funds on user's account suddenly dissappear without any transactions, the failure process of the transactions, lost of data privacy users, and so on. Some of the these phenomena happened beyond the user's control so it is hard to be solved directly. This is a form of environmental uncertainty and behavioral uncertainty as a negative problems on financial technology that not occur on conventional financial services. This has triggered an increase of perceived risk from the use of fintech services. Therefore, we should to have good awareness that financial technology on this era cannot be stopped given the increasingly needs of modern human being. In facing the growth of fintech services, we should to balancing our perspective about financial technology that has positive and negative side on it. By having these two perspectives, hopefully the fintech users can be wiser in facing the fintech advanced in modern era.

LITERATURE REVIEW

As has been demonstrated, the bank of the future in its various manifestations will be a consequence of the evolution of the current banking business model. Tere has been considerable scholarly investigation into the uniqueness of this business model, but less so on its changing nature. Song and Takor (2010) are helpful in this respect and suggest that there are three aspects to this evolution, namely competition, complementary and co-evolution. Although liquidity transformation is evolving, it remains central to a bank's role. All the dynamics mentioned are relevant to the economy. Tere is considerable evidence, as outlined

by Levine (2001), that market liberalization has a causal impact on economic growth. The impact of technology on productivity should prove positive and enhance the functioning of the domestic financial system. Indeed, market liberalization has already reshaped banking by increasing competition. New fee based ancillary financial services have become widespread, as has the proprietorial use of balance sheets. Risk has been securitized and even packaged into trade-able products. Challenger banks are developing in a complementary way with the incumbents. The latter have an advantage over new entrants because they have information on their customers. The liquidity insurance model, proposed by Diamond and Dybvig (1983), explains how such banks have informational advantages over exchange markets. That said, financial technology changes these dynamics. It is facilitating the processing of financial data by third parties, explained in greater detail in the section on Open Banking. At the same time, financial technology is facilitating banking as a service. This is where financial services are delivered by a broker over the Internet without resort to the balance sheet. This includes roboadvisory asset management, peer to peer lending, and crowd funding. Its growth will be facilitated by Open Banking as it becomes more geographically adopted. Figure 3 illustrates how these business models are disintermediating the traditional banking role and matching borrowers and savers. Meanwhile, the banking sector is co-evolving alongside a shadow banking phenomenon. Lenders and borrowers are interacting, but outside of the banking sector. This is a concern for central banks and banking regulators, as the lending is taking place in an unregulated environment. Shadow banking has grown because of financial technology, market liberalization and excess liquidity in the asset management ecosystem. Pozsar and Singh (2011) detail the non-bank/bank intersection of shadow banking. They point out that shadow banking results in reverse maturity transformation. Incumbent banks have blurred the distinction between their use of traditional (M2) liabilities and marketbased shadow banking (non-M2) liabilities. This impacts the inter-generational transfers that enable a bank to achieve interest rate smoothing.

RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

For this work, quantitative research technique was applied, whereby questionnaire survey method was used as a medium of data collection. The sample size of the research is 62 customers of the banking industry in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia. The primary data of the research includes survey of 62 respondents of customers in banking industry in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia made out of Google form. The data was assessed using the graphical statistical analysis in order to generate the financial technology findings in the banking industry in the KSA.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

Demographic Characteristics The details of the demographic findings are shown in Table 1. Based on Table 1, in terms of age, 79% were in the 18-26 years old age group, 14.5% were in the 27-35 years old age group and 6.5 % were in the age group of 36 years old and above. In terms of gender, 12.9% were males and 87.1 % were females. As for education level, 16.1% have completed high school, 77.4% have completed university degree and 6.5% have completed master's degree.

Questionnaire Analysis:

The results and findings from the survey questionnaire is presented in this section. The respondents were asked if they are aware with the term digitalization. Based on Figure 1, 32.3% strongly agreed, 33.90% were neutral and 33.90% strongly disagreed.

Next, the respondents were asked if they are aware with the term FinTech. Based on Figure 2, 27.40% strongly agreed, 38.70% were neutral and 33.90% strongly disagreed. Next, the respondents were asked if the new finance technology is better for customer services. Based on Figure 3, 53.20% strongly agreed, 33.90% were neutral and 12.90% strongly disagreed.

Next, the respondents were asked if mobile payment can be used anywhere, where payment is required? Based on Figure 4, 32.30% strongly agreed, 48.40% were neutral and 19.40% strongly disagreed. Next, the respondents were asked if involvement in emerging FinTech is necessary for the field of finance. Based on Figure 5, 40.30% strongly agreed, 51.60% were neutral and 8.10% strongly disagreed. Next, the respondents were asked if FinTech increases the security of financial transaction. Based on Figure 7, 38.70% strongly agreed, 50% were neutral and 11.30% strongly disagreed.

Overall, the findings of this study have shown that FinTech has a positive role in the banking sector of Saudi Arabia. The consumers have understood that digitalization has brought the banking industry new business models, development concepts and areas of improvements, from Internet banking to monetary transactions [13]. Thus, banks in the Kingdom have already adopted digital banking solutions as a core strategy to cater to constantly changing consumer behaviors, especially with the implementation of FinTech [14]. The budgetary innovation in Saudi Arabia tries to expand on the achievement, which is accomplished by the money related segment of the Kingdom. There are three primary destinations, which the budgetary innovation benefits in Saudi Arabia wish to achieve in the financial area. It is to quicken the development and advancement of FinTech so as to make the Kingdom a goal of advancement. Besides, so as to set up an extensive comprehension of the money related innovation and its utilization for the advancement of the financial part of Saudi Arabia. Thirdly, to make items and administrations so as to help the little and medium measured ventures to be represented considerable authority in financial technology.

CONCLUSION:

This study has analyzed the role of FinTech in the banking sector of Saudi Arabia. The overall results have shown that FinTech has improved the banking sector and has exhibited a positive impact in Saudi Arabia. Thus, FinTech has become an integral part of banking in Saudi Arabia. Consumers are benefitting from this advancement and the banks needs to keep up with the evolving technology to provide the best service for its consumers in the long run.

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